

A MIXED MODE DELAMINATION SPECIMEN AND ITS FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes a new mixed mode I+II delamination specimen, called Cantilever Beam Opened Notch (CBON). The strain energy release rate is used to characterize the onset of delamination in thick unidirectional glass/epoxy composite under static loading. This rate is determined experimentally by the compliance method, as well as by a finite element analysis. The program of finite element analysis, based on linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM), allows us to confirm experimental fracture energy measurements and to distinguish the contribution of GI and GII components in the mixed mode I+II. This separation has been verified by a test using the MMF specimens.

The excellent correlation between experimental and finite element results proves that the finite element analysis is very efficient for the prediction of mixed mode delamination. Especially, a noticeable variation in the energy release rate G_{II}/G_I can be obtained with the CBON specimens. In the case of thick glass/epoxy composite, the ratio is: $0,72 < G_{II}/G_I < 1,34$.

INTRODUCTION

The delamination between the composite layers is one of the most frequently observed failure modes in composite structure. In order to assure a greater safety in the use of these materials, we must predict a fracture criterion of delamination. Several studies have already shown that the concept of strain energy release rate in LEFM remains valid to characterize the delamination behaviour in composite, assuming that the delamination will propagate along the initial imbedment interface.

A number of authors have successfully dealt with the pure mode I (opening mode) and the pure mode II (in-plane shear mode) delamination by this concept.¹⁻⁶ But in most service conditions, the composite parts are subjected to combined loadings. In these cases, it is not enough to establish the pure mode criterions with three constants: G_{Ic} , G_{IIc} and G_{IIIc} . In an attempt to draw mixed mode I+II interlaminar failure envelope, several tests were proposed in the literature.⁷⁻¹³ As is now well known, the total critical strain energy release rate $G_{(I,II)c}$ in the mixed mode delamination increases with a G_{II}/G_I ratio,^{7,8} it is therefore important to separate the contribution of each modes GI and GII, and at the same time to determine the total critical energy values. The finite element analysis has been used in both determinations, and has been considered invaluable.^{14,15} However with each specimens proposed in the literature, the G_{II}/G_I ratio can vary only within a very limited range. Up to the present none of them has been standardized.

Glass/epoxy composite has been widely used, particularly in automotive industries. After numerous works on pure mode I and pure mode II delamination for this composite, the present study will introduce a new mixed mode test in order to investigate delamination behaviour. A finite element computer program can be employed to determine the contribution of each modes, as well as the total critical energy release rate. By the comparison of experimental and finite element results, a code of computer for fissure modeling can be identified so as to simplify experimental procedure in mixed mode delamination study for composites.

DESCRIPTION OF THE SPECIMEN CBON AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The material tested in this study, supplied by RNUR, is an epoxy M10 reinforced with 60% by volume of E-glass fibers in the form of 20mm thick panels. The elastic constants, used in the finite element analysis, are presented as follow:

$E_1=44000\text{MPa}$ $E_2=12000\text{MPa}$ $\nu=0,3$ $G_{12}=5000\text{MPa}$

The mixed mode specimens, named Cantilever Beam Opened Notch (CBON), are shown in Figure 1. It is subjected to a static flexural loading. The initial crack was formed by inserting a Teflon film at mid-thickness during moulding. Varying both free length L_1 and initial crack lengths A , we can determine the range of the variation of the G_{II}/G_I ratio for the mixed mode. In order to measure the total critical energy release rate $G_{(I,II)c}$ by the compliance method, L_1 and A were optimized with the help of the results of the finite element analysis. 6 different free lengths have been chosen, and for each of them either 4 or 5 specimens with different initial crack length were tested to establish a law of compliance.

Fig.1 The CBON Specimen

Fig.2 The Experimental Curves For $L_1=110\text{mm}$, $A=50\text{mm}$

The tests were carried out in an INSTRON 1186 machine at slow displacement speed 2mm/min. With the help of a microcomputer system, the load P , the deflection at the loading point δ , acoustic emission signals and the response of a strain gauge, placed just over the crack tip as shown in Fig.1, have been recorded during the tests. Load-deflection curve (Fig.2) shows that P increases linearly with δ until a critical value (P_c, δ_c), where the onset of crack initiation is reached. Moreover the critical points were simultaneously detected by both the acoustic emission and the response of the gauge. These techniques have perfectly identified the critical values, as shown, for example, in Fig.2. After having established a compliance ($C=\delta/P$) versus crack length relationship: $C=f(A)$, we can measure experimentally the total critical energy release rate at the onset of mixed mode delamination for glass/epoxy composite by the compliance method, expressed by

$$G_{(I,II)c} = \frac{P_c^2}{2B} \frac{\partial C}{\partial A} \quad (1)$$

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

A program of finite element model in two-dimensional problems of fracture mechanics in MEF was used, in conjunction with the meshing program MEF/MOSAIC. these programs, explained elsewhere,^{16,17} have been developed by the Division Méthodes Numériques en Mécaniques in University of Compiègne.

In this study, the specimens were meshed, as shown in Fig.3, by quadratic isoparametric elements. At the crack tip, the modified elements introduced by BARSOUM¹⁸ were employed so as to represent the singularity more accurately. Near the crack tip a relatively small grids were meshed, in which it is easy to choose a symmetric path around the crack tip for the calculation of the RICE integrals.

Introducing the critical loads P_c detected during the tests, this program allows us to determine:

- the specimen compliance as a function of $L1$ and A ;
- the total critical strain energy release rate $G(I,II)c$;
- the energy release rate contributions of mode I and mode II to the mixed mode delamination: $JI(GI)$ $JII(GII)$
- the related stress intensity factors KI and KII correspondent.

$G(I,II)c$ can be computed by giving to the initial crack only a very small virtual crack extension in mid-plane, using the following equation:

$$G = \frac{1}{2} \{U\}^T \frac{\Delta [K]}{\Delta A} \{U\} \quad (2)$$

where U is the displacement field; ΔA is the virtual crack extension; $\Delta [K]$ is the variation in the rigidity matrix caused by ΔA .

Fig.3 Finite Element Mesh

Fig.4 A J-Integral path

Since the material is considered linear elastic, $G(I,II)c$ can be obtained by the J-integrals introduced by RICE:

$$J(I,II)c = JI + JII, \quad J(I,II)c = G(I,II)c \quad (3)$$

If we consider a path Γ around the crack tip (Fig.4), invariant integrals are described as the following:

$$J_k = \int_{\Gamma} [w(\tilde{u}^k) n_1 - \sigma_{ij}(\tilde{u}^k) n_j u_i^{k,1}] ds \quad w(\tilde{u}^k) = \frac{1}{2} \sigma_{ij}(\tilde{u}^k) \epsilon_{ij}(\tilde{u}^k) \quad (4)$$

where \tilde{u}^k denotes the displacement vector, $w(\tilde{u}^k)$ the strain energy density, $\sigma_{ij}(\tilde{u}^k)$, $\epsilon_{ij}(\tilde{u}^k)$ the stress and deformation tensors, Γ the integral path, and \tilde{n} the vector normal to the path Γ .

In fact, the displacement vector can be represented as follows:

$$\{\tilde{u}\} = \{\tilde{u}^I\} + \{\tilde{u}^{II}\} \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} u1^I \\ u2^I \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{Bmatrix} u1(X1,X2) + u1(X1,-X2) \\ u2(X1,X2) - u2(X1,-X2) \end{Bmatrix} \quad \begin{Bmatrix} u1^{II} \\ u2^{II} \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{Bmatrix} u1(X1,X2) - u1(X1,-X2) \\ u2(X1,X2) + u2(X1,-X2) \end{Bmatrix}$$

For an orthotropic material, JI and JII can be related to the stress intensity factors as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 JI &= KI^2 \sqrt{S1111 S2222} A / 2, \\
 JII &= KII^2 S1111 \sqrt{A} / 2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$A = \frac{S1212 + S3333}{S1111} \sqrt{\frac{S2222}{S1111}} \quad (6)$$

where S_{ijkl} is a flexibility tensor.

According to the compliance method introduced by IRWIN-KIES¹⁹, the $G(I,II)$ can be measured by using a series of specimens with different initial crack lengths, on condition that these specimens have the same fracture mode. In other words, for a I+II mixed mode delamination their $GII/GI(JII/JI)$ must be constants. In fact this ratio is independent of load P . Consequently before tests a fictive load was used in the finite element program to estimate the varying range of the GII/GI ratio. The results allow the optimization of the free length and initial crack length for the CBN specimen used.

VERIFICATION OF THE SEPARATION OF MODE I AND MODE II WITH THE MMF SPECIMENS

The GII/GI ratio, as mentioned above, is so important that we must take care to determine it. With the CBN specimens, it is difficult to measure it experimentally. Hence thick MMF specimens of the same composite as the CBN specimens, shown in Fig.5, were tested under the same conditions described earlier in order to confirm the separation of each modes by the finite element analysis.

With the help of the same techniques, tests were conducted with a group of specimens, whose $L1$ and A dimensions had been given by the rule of the constant GII/GI ratio authorising the use of the compliance method. This ratio had been pre-calculated by the finite element program. As a result the specimens tested have a fixed free length: 110mm, initial crack length of which varies from 30mm to 60mm. In this case, GII/GI is nearly kept unchanged about 0,58.

Fig.5 Mixed Mode Flexural Specimen

During the tests not only the load and deflection can be recorded, more important, by instrumenting an extensometer on the specimens, but also the opening displacement δL between two lips at the loading point can be also found. The compliance is computed using the following equation:

$$CL = \frac{\delta L}{(P/2)} \quad (7)$$

CL merely depends on mode I, and is treated as the same deformation as the DCB specimens (Fig.5). As seen, the experimental energy release rate to mode I component can be measured by using

$$GI = \frac{(P/2)^2}{2B} \frac{\partial CL}{\partial A} \quad (8)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Separation of Mode I and Mode II

For the CBN specimen, a simplified approach based on beam theory separating the load into a symmetric loading and an antisymmetric loading corresponding respectively to mode I and mode II, leads to the following expression for the GII/GI ratio:

$$\frac{G_{II}}{G_I} = \frac{3}{4} \frac{1}{\{1+6EI/[5(L1-A)^2 GF]\}} \quad (9)$$

According to Equ.(9) this ratio depends on (L1-A), and remains lower than 0.75. When (L1-A) tends towards infinity, it approaches 0.75 for any material.²⁰

However for the CBON specimen, the results of the finite element analysis for three different materials illustrate that:

- I. For a given free length L1 the GII/GI ratio is virtually independent of initial crack length A, provided that A doesn't vary in a large range. In this case the compliance method can be used.²⁰
- II. As L1 increases, this ratio tends towards a constant, which takes different values for different materials but not 0,75 anyway.(Fig.6) For glass/epoxy composite, this constant is equal to 0.72.
- III. The GII/GI ratio varies within a range which seems proportional to the E11/G12 ratio of the material. For the composite used in this study, as far as we know, this range is $0,72 < G_{II}/G_I < 1,34$.

Figure 7 presents the compliances CL corresponding to mode I component obtained from opening displacements for MMF specimens. As well seen, experimental and finite element values have a excellent concordance. Table 1. lists mode I contribution to the total energy release rate, determined by different methods. These results convince ourself of the separation of mode I and modeII in mixed mode by the finite element analysis. As a essential result, computation by finite element method has found that for the MMF specimens the GI/GI ratio can vary from 0.46 to 0.72 with L1 and A instead of a constant, indicated by VANDERCLEY.¹⁰

Fig.6 The Variation of The GII/GI Ratio

Fig.7 The Opening Compliances For MMF

Table 1. mode I contribution to the total energy release rate for the-MMF specimens

L1-- A(mm)	Pc/2 (N)	J ^{FE} (J/M ²)	G ^{FE-C} (J/M ²)	G ^{EXP-C} (J/M ²)	GII/GI a)
110--35	575	480.7	477.3	544.3	0.5562
110--40	454	367.3	376.3	392.0	0.5740
110--45	393	330.9	340.1	332.3	0.5893
110--45	387	320.9	329.8	322.2	0.5893
110--60	300	309.9	301.8	263.0	0.6227
MOYENNE		361.9±119	365.1±112	370.8±174	0.5863±0.04

a). J^{FE} -- J-integral by FE; G^{FE-C}-- compliance method for compliances by FE; G^{EXP-C}-- compliance method for experimental compliances.

2. Analytical and Experimental Compliances

In Fig.8 and Fig.9, compliances are plotted versus crack lengths for the CBON and the MMF specimens respectively. They show that experimental values are usually a bit of larger than those of finite element. A reasonable explanation reposes on the damage observed near embedding region when gripping, which influences experimental deflection. On the contrary the points deduced from the simple beam theory are far away from the experimental points. Since this theory is not able to take into account the complex stress and

strain fields at the crack tip, it is not too much to say that in certain cases the simple beam theory perhaps is no longer suitable.

Fig.8 The Compliances For The MMF Specimens

Fig.9 The Compliances For The CBON Specimens

3. Critical Strain Energy Release Rate

Table 2. Critical Strain Energy Release rate

NOM	L1--(A)mm	JII/JI	b) J ^{FE} (J/M ²)	JII ^{FE} (J/M ²)	J(I,II) _c ^{FE}	G(I,II) _c ^{FE}	G(I,II) _c ^{FE-C}	G(I,II) _c ^{EXP-C}
CBON	65--(25-35)	1.2487±0.16	805.9±165	1006.4±205	1812.3±370	1804.3±388		
CBON	85--(25-45)	1.0228±0.07	702.0±101	716.4±162	1422.1±260	1420.4±283	1437.9±308	1629.4±411
CBON	110--(30-50)	0.8896±0.03	499.6±101	446.3±97	945.8±198	954.6±207	990.6±260	1076.6±194
CBON	125--(35-65)	0.8502±0.02	436.6±107	371.0±84	807.6±184	823.2±196	840.0±228	921.4±387
CBON	140--(45-65)	0.8170±0.01	427.7±114	349.3±69	777.1±205	766.4±184	829.5±213	738.7±159
CBON	150--(55-75)	0.7958±0.01	383.3±60	305.2±47	688.5±107	715.7±119	746.7±116	661.8±179
MMF	110--(35-60)	0.5867±0.03	362.0±119	211.1±56	573.2±175	556.2±169	563.7±154	611.5±58

b). J^{FE} -- J-integral by FE; G^{FE-C}--compliance method for compliances by FE;

G^{FE}-- virtual crack extension method by FE; G^{EXP-C}-- compliance method for experimental compliances.

Fig.10 Total Fracture Energy as a Function of Shear Loading Contribution

Table 2 provides all the critical energy release rate values determined by different methods for glass/epoxy composite. It can be seen that there are no great differences between finite element results $J(I,II)_c^{FE}$, $G(I,II)_c^{FE}$ and $G(I,II)_c^{FE-C}$, based on three different methods. Both for the CBON and MMF specimens, a second order polynomial of the form $C = a+bA+cA^2$ (where a,b,c are constants) was used as same as shown in Fig.7. In addition, by the comparison of $G(I,II)_c^{FE}$ and $G(I,II)_c^{EXP-C}$, the deviation is within a $\pm 13\%$ range.

For glass/epoxy composite it must be indicated that in the mixed mode I+II case, not only the total critical energy release rate increases with the G_{II}/G_I ratio, but also does both the contribution of mode I and mode II. For the interpretation of this fact that the resistance to opening mode delamination is increased by the shear deformation due to mode II. Nevertheless in the other mixed mode cases, the constant contribution of mode I was observed.⁷ Comparing critical values of pure mode I and pure mode II for the same composite, $G_{Ic}=200 \text{ J/M}^2$ and $G_{IIc}=3000 \text{ J/M}^2$, obtained in the preceding studies,^{6,21} an explanation for this behaviour of the glass/epoxy composite may be a direct result of the unusually large difference between two values. This needs an examination at the microscope scale to explain the exact delamination mechanics in the mixed mode fracture problem for composites.

A simple representation of this mixed mode results is shown in Figure 10. It is apparent that around 50% of the $G_{II}/G(I,II)c$ ratio a remarkable change in behaviour occurs. The critical fracture energy increases rapidly in this range, for a relatively small increase in the ratio $G_{II}/G(I,II)c$. It means that there is a possible transition from a mode I dominated to a mixed mode failure.

CONCLUSION

1. With the thick CBON specimens the mixed mode I+II delamination is characterized, for a glass/epoxy composite, by a G_{II}/G_I ratio varying between 0.72 and 1.34.
2. The finite element analysis, based on the linear elastic fracture mechanics, is very useful to predict the critical energy release rate envelope in mixed mode delamination. Moreover it can correctly separate the contribution of each modes.
3. The compliance method allows the experimental measurement of the critical energy value in mixed mode. In the case of the Thick CBON and MMF specimens, the laws of compliance are of the form: $C=a+bA+cA^2$, instead of a third order polynomial as usual.
4. For thick glass/epoxy, experimental results using the CBON and MMF specimens present a transition in the delamination behaviour. As the proportion of mode II is increased nearby 50%, the delamination resistance shows a remarkable increase.
5. The simple beam theory showed unable to predict the mixed mode delamination, especially for a thick beam.

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